

DESIGN OF LOW POWER 9T SRAM CELL WITH EXPANDED NOISE MARGIN

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ABSTRACT

SRAM (Static random access memory) cells operate at lower power supply voltages with higher stability got major attention due to their utmost demand in advanced microelectronics devices. In scaled technologies, the power dissipation and stability of SRAM cells become of prime importance due to the aggressive supply voltage scaling. In this context, a novel 9T SRAM memory cell has been proposed with a commendable improvement in both read stability and write stability of the cell along with a reduction in power dissipation. The characteristics parameters of the proposed 9T SRAM cell are compared with state-of-the-art designs like six transistors (6T), tunable access transistors 8T (TA8T), D2P11T (data dependent power supply 11T), and 11T SRAM cells. The RSNM (read static noise margin) of the novel proposed 9T SRAM cell is enhanced by 1.95×, 1.92×, 1.87×, 1.90× as of 6T, TA8T, D2P11T and 11T SRAM cells respectively. It occurs as a result by utilization of an isolated read port during read operation. Further, the write ability of the proposed 9T SRAM cell is increased by 1.12×, 1.05×, 1.12×, 1.14× as of 6T, TA8T, D2P11T and 11T SRAM cells respectively. The read power of 9T SRAM cells also gets reduced by 1.48×, 1.16×, 1.38×, 1.66× as of 6T, TA8T, D2P11T, 11T SRAM cells. In addition to this, read access time of the proposed 9T cell is reduced by 1.08×, 1.01×, 1.04×, 1.15× as of 6T, TA8T, D2P11T, 11T SRAM cells. In proposed 9T cell, the I_{on} to I_{off} ratio is larger, i.e., 3.5×, 3.45×, 3.54×, as compared to 6T, TA8T, 11T SRAM cells. It shows the applicability of a 9T SRAM cell for a large density array. The simulation work has been performed with Cadence Virtuoso at the 45nm technology node.

Keywords: *Microelectronics, Low power VLSI design, SRAM, Power consumption, stability.*

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, a tremendous boom has been observed in the design and development of IoT and machine learning-based devices [1]. These technologies are used in modern electronic devices for facial expression recognition, speech recognition, and video surveillance [2-3]. In a recognition system, computation is performed through a high-performance processor that utilizes an on-chip cache memory to access the information. Such a system is always remains in active mode and requires extended battery life to sustain the operation [4]. Since, SRAM cell occupies a significant part of the system on chip area and consume large power. Therefore, designing an energy-efficient and stable SRAM cell is of prime importance for advanced microelectronics devices. The supply voltage scaling is a highly promising technique to decline the dynamic power consumption due to its quadratic dependency on supply voltage [5]. Further, static power

dissipation rises exponentially due to an increase in sub-threshold and gate leakage currents with reduced supply voltage. In addition, the stability of the memory cell decreases as the voltage difference between the threshold voltage [6] and the supply voltage is reduced. This tends to increase the read/write failure probability of the circuit. Hence, reduction in both leakage and dynamic power becomes necessary in deep sub-micron technologies. Additionally, an increase in access time has been observed with supply voltage scaling that up-surge the total energy per read/write cycle. Fig. 1 (a) and (b) represent the schematic and layout diagram, respectively for a 6T SRAM cell.

Fig.1. (a) The 6T cell schematic (b) 6T cell layout

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

To cope with the issues associated with 6T SRAM cell, numerous works [8-15] have been reported in the literature. To increase the RSNM in SRAM cells, read buffer transistors [8] and isolated read structures [9] are most commonly used approaches. An 8T SRAM cell [8] reported with the same basic configuration as in 6T cell. The two transistors are added in the pull-down network to enhance the read stability of 8T cell. Additionally, one more

transistor is employed in the pull-down network in order to mitigate the power consumption. In [9], read decoupled structure along with positive feedback is utilized to get scale down in static power dissipation and enrichment in stability of the cell. K. Cho et al. [10] presented a highly stable 9T SRAM cell that operates in near-threshold area and supports the bit-interleaving structure. The write assist methodology is used with selective power gating to enhance the write ability. He et al. [11] investigated the 11T SRAM cell that operates at a lower supply voltage. A built-in write/read assist technique is used to enhance the write ability and RSNM. Further, the soft error issue has been resolved by bit-interleaving array structure. Harekrishana et al. [12], have reported a 12T SRAM cell that operates at ultra-low power supply voltage. During write and read operations, this cell works in differential and single-ended mode respectively. This cell shows a significant decline in power dissipation along with enhancement in RSNM. Further, the power cut-off technique is used to increase in write ability. In [13], a power-efficient 12T SRAM cell is proposed with the read decoupled structure that enhances the RSNM of the cell. Additionally, the write ability is enhanced by dynamic loop-cutting methodology. Technology node scaling results an increase in leakage current. N. Tiwari et al. [14] have investigated an asymmetrical 9T SRAM cell with MTCMOS methodology to mitigate the static power.

In [15], the 7T SRAM cell is operates in single-ended mode in read/write operations. The power consumption is reduced with improvement in cell stability. Additionally, the write power of the cell also gets minimized by employing supply feedback. An 11 T SRAM cell has been designed by V. Sharma et al. [16]. The RSNM of the cell gets improved by using read decoupled structure whereas write ability has been enhanced by feedback cutting technique. The 8T SRAM cell with reduction in power dissipation and improved write access time is presented by C. Roy et al. [17]. In this memory cell, transmission gates are used as access transistors to improve the write delay. Also, a stack transistor is employed to minimize the leakage power dissipation. L. Wen et al. [18] have investigated a tunable access 8T SRAM cell. The strength of the access transistors is tuned by adding two extra transistors in order to get improvement in write ability. In addition, RSNM of the cell gets improved due to an increase in pull-down strength during the read operation. In [19], reduction in power dissipation is achieved by utilizing the

data-dependent power supply rather than an exclusive power supply. Also, RSNM of the cell is enhanced by read decoupled methodology. In [20], both read stability and write ability are improved by operating the 11T SRAM cell in differential and single-ended mode, respectively. Considering various challenges and trade-offs, authors have attempted to design and investigate a 9T SRAM topology characterized by reduced power dissipation, improved stability, and moderate access time. The proposed novel 9T SRAM cell is presented.

1. In the proposed 9T SRAM cell, read and write power consumptions are declined by 1.48×, 1.09×, as compared to the 6T SRAM cell. Additionally, both read/write power dissipation in the proposed 9T SRAM cell is minimum as of all reference cells.

2. The RSNM and WSNM are increased by 1.95×, 1.12× as of 6T SRAM cell. Also, the highest values of WSNM (write static noise margin and RSNM (read static noise margin) are observed in the proposed 9T SRAM cell, among other cells.

3. The read delay is significantly improved by 1.08×, 1.01×, 1.05×, and 1.15× as of 6T, TA8T, D2P11T, and 11T SRAM cells.

4. The I_{on} to I_{off} ratio of the proposed 9T SRAM cell is enhanced by 3.5× as compared to the 6T SRAM cell. It dictates the ability to handle a large bit cell array.

The rest of the paper is written in the following way: Section 3 includes the detailed read as well as write mechanism of the proposed 9T SRAM cell. Section 4 includes the detailed analysis of obtained simulated results. Finally, Section 5 represents the concluding remarks of the work.

3. 9T SRAM CELL SCHEMATIC AND OPERATION

In 9T SRAM cell, the basic core latch structure incorporates of cross-coupled inverter pairs of PM1, NM1, and PM2, NM3 transistors shown in Fig. 2(a). The NM2 and NM4 transistors are added in pull down path of both left and right side inverters. The NM5 transistor works as an access device used to write the available data to storage node Q. This NM5 transistors regulated by WWL i.e. write word line signal. The RWL i.e. read word line signal is used to turn on the NM6 transistor, providing the read path through the NM7 transistor

during read operation. Fig. 2(b) dictates the signal status during read and write operations along with the hold mechanism. The RBL i.e., read bit-line signal is connected to V_{DD} whereas the virtual ground (VGND) signal has been placed at logic '0'.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2. (a) Schematic of 9T SRAM cell (b) Status of control signal

Further, read word line signal is also connected to V_{DD} during read function as depicted in Fig. 3(a). In order to perform the read '0' operation, initially storage node Q and Q_{bar} are placed at logic '0' and

logic '1' respectively. This activates the NM7 transistor and provides the discharge path to the RBL signal through NM6 and NM7 devices. The generated read transient waveform is depicted in Fig. 4(a). During write '0' function, logic '0' and logic '1' are considered at write bit-line (WBL) and WWL signals respectively. The VGND and RWL signals are shifted to logic '1' and logic '0' respectively as shown in Fig. 3(b). The available data i.e., logic '1' at node Q starts to discharge through NM5 transistor. The input voltage at the gates of NM1 and NM2 transistors start to decrease and become lower than the threshold voltage and turn-off both the transistors. Subsequently, PM1 transistor becomes on and results logic '1' at node Qb. It results in single ended write mode operation in the proposed 9T SRAM cell.

Fig. 3. (a) Read '0' function (b) Write '0' function of 9T SRAM cell

The resulting write transient waveform is mentioned in Fig. 4(b). In static mode, logic '0' is set to both WWL and RWL signals. The path between storage nodes and bit-lines becomes breaks, and the stored data remains preserved in hold state.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. 9T- SRAM cell (a) Read transient wave form (b) Write transient waveform.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The projected 9T SRAM cell and other referenced cells are simulated at 45nm technology node for fair comparison. In proposed 9T SRAM cell, the width of pull-up transistors (PM1 and PM2) is kept lower to achieve a pull-up ratio less than one which helps in easy write operation. The NM1 and NM3 transistors are kept quite strong as these transistors participate in the discharging path during hold function. The transistors i.e. NM2 and NM4, are kept weaker to provide higher resistive path during this hold function. The read path transistors NM6 and NM7 are taken large enough to achieve reasonable RSNM. The write assist transistor (NM5) is also kept quite large to transfer the data from bit-lines to the storage node. Additionally, 9T SRAM cell characteristics like read/write power, leakage power, read access time, write access time, read stability, write stability, bit-line leakage current, i.e., I_{off}, read current i.e. I_{on}, and I_{on}/I_{off} ratio are investigated in detail.

4.1 Read and Write Power Dissipation

It has been reported that more than 75% of the power is consumed by the embedded SRAM in silicon-on-chip devices [21]. The overall power dissipation is the sum of both dynamic and static power dissipation. The occurrence of switching events and supply voltages majorly affected the dynamic power due to their direct relationship, like CV_{dd}^2 . In this work, average value read power consumption is computed with consideration that logic '1' is accumulated at node Qb. Fig. 5(a) represents variations in read power with change in supply voltage. In 9T SRAM cell, read power consumption is declined by 1.48×, 1.16×, 1.38×, 1.66× as of 6T, TA8T, D2P11T, and 11T SRAM cells. This happens because of the read-decoupled structure in which the pre-charging of bit-lines is less because of a single-ended operation for read mode and also offers a reduction in activity factor.

Further, the highest swing voltage at the NM6 transistor single node rises to the supply voltages compared to the dual node as in the case of differential read structure. The write power consumption is measured when logic '0' is written at the node Q. Fig. 5(b) depicts the write power with change in supply mode voltage. The finding represents that the write power of 9T SRAM cell is decreased by 1.09×, 1.32×, 1.12×, 1.25× as of 6T, TA8T, D2P11T, and 11T SRAM cells. This occurs due to a reduction in activity factor and bit-line

capacitance. The maximum write power is observed due to the larger activity factor during differential write operation in the TA8T SRAM cell.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. (a) Variation in read power vs change in supply voltage (b) Variation in write power vs change in supply voltage

4.2 Leakage Power Dissipation

With the shifting of the technology node below 90 nm, the leakage power becomes a very prominent factor in achieving an overall reduction in power dissipation [22]. It is well known that a major section of the SRAM cache memory remains

in hold mode and consumes the leakage power. Fig. 6(a) shows the leakage power of the proposed 9T SRAM cell and considered cells at various voltages. The leakage power of the proposed 9T SRAM cell has been observed that is minimized by 1.41×, 1.75×, 1.45× and 1.40×, as of 6T, TA8T, D2P11T, and 11T SRAM cells. It occurs because of the stacking of NM2 and NM4 devices that increases the resistivity in the core latch circuitry. It results in a very amount of small leakage power in the 9T SRAM cell. Fig. 6(b) depicts the change in leakage power with variation in temperature. It is evident that leakage power increases exponentially in all SRAM cells with a rise in temperature. Moreover, The leakage power variation of 9T SRAM cell is minimum for the temperature range -25 °C to 100 °C as of achieved in all reference cells. This is credited to the core-latch circuitry of the 9T SRAM cell.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6. (a) Leakage power in pw v/s supply voltage (b) Leakage power in pw v/s changed in temperature °C

4.3 Read And Write Access Time

Read/write access time denotes the performance of SRAM cells. During read operation by the single-ended, the read access time is defined as the time difference between the activation of the read word line signal and discharging the bit line to a voltage difference of 50 mV from their initial pre-charge level [23]. During the differential read operation, read access time is expressed as the time needed to discharge one of the bitlines to a voltage difference with the other bitline after turning on of the read word line signal.

The read delay is calculated when the RWL signal rises to $V_{dd}/2$ and the bit-line is discharged to $V_{dd}/2$ in the proposed 9T and considered SRAM cells. In this article, read access time is attributed to discharge time through NM6 and NM7 transistors. The calculated values of the read delay of all the cells at various voltages are depicted in Fig. 7(a). This has been observed that read access time of 9T SRAM cell is decreased by 1.08×, 1.01×, 1.05×, and 1.15× as of 6T, TA8T, D2P11T, and 11T SRAM cells. This occurs because of the dynamic threshold voltage technique, which is used to reduce the discharging time of the read bit-line of the 9T SRAM cell. Further, it is pertinent that the read delay in the proposed 9T SRAM cell is minimum at 0.5V supply voltage among all referenced cells. It may be the cause of higher read current flow through the read bit-line. Moreover, an

increase in the access time has been noticed with a decrease in supply voltage.

Write delay for write logic ‘1’ is expressed as the time gap to develop 0.5V of V_{dd} at the write word-line signal (WWL) and charge the storage node till 90% of V_{dd}. Whereas to write logic ‘0’ the time needed to raise WWL to 0.5V of V_{dd} and discharge the node up to 10% of V_{dd}. In SRAM cells, write operation influenced by the sizing of pull-up and access transistors. Therefore, these transistors are sized with an equal aspect ratio in all SRAM cells. Fig. 7(b) portrays the comparison between calculated values of write delay of all SRAM cells at various voltages. An increase in write delay of the projected 9T cell has been noticed in compared to 6T, TA8T, and D2P11T SRAM cells. This occurs due to a circuit structure i.e. single-ended write structure, which takes longer time to develop up to 90% of V_{dd} at the data storage node. However, the write access time is smaller for the proposed 9T SRAM cell as compared to 11T SRAM cell, while both cells are operated in single-ended mode during write operation. The minimum write delay has been noticed in 6T cells as of referenced topologies. It may be attributed to their differential structure.

(b)

Fig. 7. (a) Change in read access time (ps) with variation in Supply voltage (V) (b) Change in write access time(ps) with variation in supply voltage(v)

4.4 Read/Write Stability of Memory Cell

Stability is expressed in terms of direct current noise voltage, which can be withstood without change in storage node data of memory cells. In the 6T memory cell, the storage node's data flipped due to an access transistor conflict issue at a lower-level supply voltage. Additionally, the voltage divider effect that develops the potential between access and pull-down transistors. When this potential becomes larger than the threshold level (voltage) of the pull-down transistor of another side inverter. It results in the destructive read operation. This can be avoided by keeping the higher cell ratio, which mentioned a smaller voltage at the data node stored logic ‘0’. In order to resolve this issue, single-ended read operation, write operations are performed in the proposed 9T SRAM cell. The butterfly curve methodology is utilized to estimate the RSNM of all SRAM cells [20].

Initially, storage node voltage at node Q has been varied and traced to the voltage at node Qb. Thereafter, voltage at node Qb has been varied, and voltage at storage node Q has been plotted, which formed a butterfly curve with two lobes. The largest square has been fitted inside the lobe of the butterfly curve. The RSNM is measured through the side length of the square. The plotted butterfly curves of all SRAM cells are depicted in Fig. 8(a). Fig. 8(b) shows the variation in RSNM at different

(a)

voltages. RSNM of proposed 9T SRAM cell is enhanced by 1.95×/ 1.92×/1.90×/ 1.87× as of 6T, TA8T, D2P11T, and 11T SRAM cells. This occurs due to the isolated read-bit-line structure that prevents the development of bit-line noise at the storage nodes. The write ability of SRAM cells is investigated through WSNM.

applied on the bit-line, and WL voltage is swept from 0V to V_{dd}. The difference lies between WL and V_{dd} voltage at which the nodes Q_b and Q flip the stored data, which represents the WSNM of the cell [21]. A bigger value of write margin signifies the ease of writing in the SRAM cell [26]. The calculated values of WSNM are depicted in Fig. 9(a).

Fig. 8. (a) VTC i.e., Voltage transfer curve of the conv. 6T, TA8T, D2p11T, 11T and proposed 9T memory cell

Fig. 8. (b) Read static noise margin(mv) vs Supply voltage(v)

Fig. 9. (a) Change in WSNM with variation in supply voltage(v) (b) Monte Carlo simulation plot of write transient waveform for 2000 samples

To measure the WSNM, various techniques are reported [24–25] in the literature. In this work, the bit-line voltage sweep [25] method has been used to determine the WSNM. In this method, data is

The WSNM of 9T SRAM cell is enhanced by 1.12×, 1.05×, 1.15×, and 1.14× as of 6T, TA8T,

D2P11T, and 11T SRAM cells. This is attributable to the word-line boosting technique and feedback loop cutting transistor (PM3). The Monte-Carlo simulation with write operation has been executed for 2000 samples. It is evident from Fig. 9(b) that the write operation for all samples is run successfully.

4.5 I_{on}/I_{off} Ratio

The read current i.e., I_{on} is measured during read mode operation when the read bit-line signal is discharged through NM6 and NM7 transistors. Fig. 10(a) depicts the variation in read current at different voltages. It has been noticed that the 9T cell has the maximum read current of 6T, TA8T, D2P11T, and 11T SRAM cells. This is because of the dynamic threshold voltage technique utilized in NM6 and NM7 transistors that results in higher current flow through the read path. Bit-line leakage current (I_{off}) was described as the current flowing through the read bit-line in static mode. The estimated values of the I_{on}/I_{off} ratio at different supply voltages are displayed in Fig. 10(b). The finding shows that the I_{on}/I_{off} ratio of 9T SRAM cell is enhanced by $3.5\times/3.45\times/3.54\times$ as of 6T, TA8T, and 11T memory cells. However, the magnitude of the I_{on}/I_{off} ratio for D2P11T SRAM cell is the highest among all reference cells. It may happen due to the smallest I_{off} (bit line leakage current) in the D2P11T SRAM cell.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 10. (a) Read current (μA) vs supply voltage (v), (b) Parameter I_{on}/I_{off} ratio vs supply voltages (v)

4.6 Area

The SRAM layout area imposes a tight transistor density and poses several design challenges between schematic and post-layout simulation. The device aspect ratio is taken very precisely to get improvements in design metric parameters like stability, access time, power dissipation, and area. The layout design process is carried out with Design Rule Checking (DRC) and then matched with the actual schematic via LVS. The parasitic capacitances are evaluated through the RC extraction process. The layouts of all SRAM cells are depicted in Figs. 11(a), 11(b), 11(c), and 11(d), accordingly. The proposed 9T SRAM cell, TA8T, D2P11T, and 11T SRAM cells represent an area overhead of $1.61\times$, $1.11\times$, $1.91\times$, and $1.78\times$ as compared with the 6T SRAM cell. The proposed 9T cell imposes a penalty in respect of increased area. However, its improvement in characteristics like higher stability and a higher I_{on}/I_{off} ratio facilitates an increase in higher bit-cell density.

Fig. 11. Layouts of (a) 8T SRAM cell (b) D2p11T cell (c) 11T SRAM cell (d) Proposed 9T SRAM cell

Table-1 Comparison of Different Design Matrix Parameters of Proposed 9T and Considered SRAM Cells

Parameters		Conv. 6T	TA8T [18]	D2p11T [19]	11T [20]	Proposed 9T Cell
Power	Read Power (μW)	2.59(1.48 \times)	2.04(1.16 \times)	2.42(1.38 \times)	2.92(1.66 \times)	1.75(1 \times)
	Write Power (nW)	45.4(1.09 \times)	55.1(1.32 \times)	46.7(1.12 \times)	52(1.25 \times)	41.5(1 \times)
	Leakage Power (pW)	11.9(1.41 \times)	14.7(1.75 \times)	12.2(1.45 \times)	11.8(1.4 \times)	8.4(1 \times)
	Read Current	14.5(0.97 \times)	14.7(0.98 \times)	14.6(0.97 \times)	14.3(0.95 \times)	14.9(1 \times)

	(μA)					
Stability	RSNM (mV)	177(0.511 \times)	180(0.52 \times)	185(0.534 \times)	182(0.526 \times)	346(1 \times)
	WSNM (mV)	322(0.877 \times)	345(0.95 \times)	322(0.88 \times)	318(0.876 \times)	363(1 \times)
Speed	Read Access time (pS)	52.61(1.08 \times)	49.6(1.01 \times)	51.1(1.04 \times)	56.1(1.15 \times)	48.67(1 \times)
	Write Access time (pS)	84.12(0.5 \times)	87(0.51 \times)	148(0.88 \times)	175(1.04 \times)	168(1 \times)
Ion/Ioff		2.31(3.50 \times)	2.34(3.45 \times)	9.2(0.87 \times)	2.28(3.54 \times)	8.09(1 \times)
Relative Area		0.62	0.69	1.1	1.18	1
Vdd		0.8 V	0.8 V	0.8 V	0.8 V	0.8 V

Table 1 summarized the design metric parameters of referenced cells and proposed 9T SRAM cells. It is interesting to note that read/write power consumptions of the proposed 9T SRAM cell are lowest among the all considered SRAM topologies. Further, improvements in both read and write stability have been noticed as of all considered SRAM cells. This is quite interesting that the 9T RSAM cell has the smallest read access time of all referenced SRAM cells. However, the write access time of 6T, TA8T, and D2P11T SRAM cells. It may happen due to their differential write operations. Further, the proposed 9T cell has a smaller write access time than the 11T SRAM cell. However, both are operated in single mode during the write operation.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In the presented work, a low-power, single-ended novel 9T SRAM cell has been designed and characterized using a Cadence Virtuoso tool for 45 nm gate length. An extensive comparative analysis is performed between the proposed 9T cell and reference cells to prove the novelty and worth, as shown in Table 1. The key observations include the reduction in read, write, and leakage power, improvement in read access time, and higher read/write stability. The proposed cell utilizes feedback and transistor stacking techniques in order to mitigate the leakage power and increase the WSNM of the cell. Further, the increase in the Ion/Ioff ratio also signifies the higher bit-cell density. Hence, the proposed 9T SRAM cell can be the most suitable circuit for ultra-low power applications.

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